

ON THE QUESTION OF THE FREE WILL UTILIZING DIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS

Eliezer Bar–Meir*

G. P. Fort Riley
650 Huebner Rd,
Fort Riley, KS 66442-4030
ORCID: 0000-0001-9200-4196

Genick Bar–Meir

Potto Project NFP
Skokie, Illinois 60076
Email: barmeir at gmail dot com
ORCID: 0000-0003-3285-7837

ABSTRACT

The debate of the free will has been argued by many over thousands of years. On one hand, there were those who believe in the free will and based on this idea, many legal and others decisions have been made. On the other hand, there are those who view the issue as predetermined. Searle a leading proponent that this approach arguing that all the decisions are actually based physical process which are only a respond to physical and chemical stimuli. In this paper, a different approach is proposed for analyzing this issue. Here, it is suggested that both sides are right but only at certain situations.

Key Words

Free will, What is Free Will, Punishment, Veto Power, Deterministic Behavior, Gray Areas of Free Will, Dimensional Analysis, Benefits of Free Will

1 Introduction

The ancient question whether or not the “free will” exist is discussed here. Almost all Religious/theological views are based on idea that “free will” exist. The whole theology of many (pseudo) monotheistic based or evolved around “free will” which was dominated since the antequate. Concepts such as sin and punishment are rooted in the idea of “free will.” Google Scholar offers over five (5) millions of books and articles about the free will. This sheer number is indication to the importance of this question. All of these books and articles take the position either that there is free will or that there isn’t free will. None has a different position that there is a (gray) zone between these

two camps. There is perhaps only one case (that was reviewed) that suggest that there is a possibility of different solution (Libet 1999). Honderich asked the question “[m]ight it be that both sides are wrong, in more than one way?” And he answered it in Honderich’s (1993) words “[j]ust as it has to be true that either you’re over six feet tall or you’re not.”

Searle (2013) and other pointed out that all the humans are physical objects must obey physical laws. Hence, he and other conclude there is no really a “free will.” According to this view one action activates another such neuron triggered by an electrical pulse from the nerve system which cause motion of the hand for example. Taylor (2021) suggested that people are actually “Like marionettes and machines.” Other like Watson (2003) citing Thomas Nagel (1979) shows example “pointing to bird [failing] into the path of one s bullet?” Others argue that there “a problem of free will is another instance of a general difficulty in bringing together our views of ourselves both as moral beings and as creatures of nature.”

As Thomas Nagel suggests in ‘Moral Luck’, the problem arises from an apparent clash between an ‘internal’ ‘subjective’ view of ourselves, as agents, unified centres and sources of activity, and an ‘external’, ‘objective’ view from which one’s [behavior] appears as ‘part of the course of events’. In Nagel’s words, ‘the self which acts and is the object of moral [judgment] is threatened with dissolution by the absorption of its acts and impulses into the class of events’.

These arguments are more philosophical in the sense as the more similar to arguments about whether the Earth is flat before people explore the universe. Today, it is widely accepted that the Earth is not flat even though, some might still hold the opinion that Earth is flat. The question for the free will is the situation today different when it was argued 40 or 50 years ago. Today there are scientific tools that were not available and not known

*All correspondence should address this author.

to the philosophy circles which perfectly understandable for this topic and maybe others.

2 The Gray Areas

The two sides of the conflict armed them self with the heavy gun arguments for “all or nothing” discussion. That is in other words, there are two camps who situated on two banks of argument with two opposing views. Yet, both camps do not believe that there is a shade of gray between their positions. Everything for these camps is either black or white. The literature review shows that this possibility is not an option for these comps and no one discuss this possibility seriously. While Libet (1999) suggested that there might be area between two banks yet he did attempt to investigate this possibility.

If one assumes that there is a shade of gray between these two positions in this dispute then it gives raise to two questions; Is there a logical source(s) or explanation for the gray zone, and, two if the first question is correct/answered: how to differentiate between these two zones. Actually the science of physics, engineering, and chemistry is full of cases where some of results are predictable and sometime the results are not. The dimensional analysis is a scientific discipline that deals with distinction between different zones among other things. This paper is intend for liberal art audience and hence, explanation what is dimensional analysis and its usages are also presented.

3 Common Undetermined Situations in Physics

A review of issue at hand, shows that initially people perceive that everyone has ability to make a decision as a “free will.” In fact, the whole penal system has been based on this idea that people are punished for their “bad” behavior because of they choose to do so. There were no real challenge to the “free will” concept until the turning point in which science weight got a strong foot hold in the society. For example, Searle suggest to look from biological point of view (classical physics). He observed that there are neurons that fire the action and assent every thing obey Newton law and other physical laws. Based on these observations there is no free will. He further explain that the feeling of free will as illusion (Searle 2013).

Those who familiar with quantum mechanics can point to Schrödinger’s equation demonstrates there is the uncertainty principle in which the location or even number of electrons can be indeterminable. In fact, the general media refers to this kind situation as as the Schrödinger’s cat (see for sitcom like Big Bang Theory). It fact, even the popular culture, this uncertainty principle is well known and documented. It impossible to predict earth quick, weather etc. This inability is not because that there are no powerful enough computer but because the butterfly effect. Experts only talk about chances that something could occur not zero or one case. In thermo–fluid science, the butterfly effect is

well known and documented. The butterfly effect refers to situation in which a small butterfly moves slightly its wing and a huge hurricanes are created as result due to this movement. In thermo–fluid there is issue of turbulence which is unpredictable and thus calculate by statistical means rather then deterministic approach. In medicine it is common to state that medicine statistically cure something rather than 100%. Actually there hardly situations that one can say that it is 100% cure in medicine.

It is not these situations only occur but they are the majority in many fields of the hard science. Hence these situations are indication for gray area. Thus, now the attention should be turned to how these gray areas in fluid mechanics, biology and quantum physics connected with what happens in the brain. Brain contains many neurons which act like a switch board or better like a motherboard. But as oppose to computer mother board, the brain requires blood supply, mass transfer and lubrication (omega 3 etc). Without these supplies the brain stop to function. Blood flows normally in a laminar pattern which is ordinary and this point seems to support Searle’s camp. Research demonstrates that the laminar flow can turn to be turbulent with a tiny disturbance. This transition is the part of the uncertainty that can happen and decisions can go either way. This only one example how the transition can occur.

The intuition that there something wrong with the approach all or nothing lead to Kane to develop the Libertarian theories (Kane 1998). Recently there were some who considered the inconsistency in both camps and tied the inconsistency to the luck (Haji 2005). Lemos (2011) argue that initial conditions (early action(s) and it is phrased in more precise manner.) are irrelevant. All these arguments are actually are refined arguments of the these two comps. While these refined arguments could lead eventually to development of the gray area(s) understanding, they are still in the stage of of the two camps ideology.

4 Dimensional Analysis

Dimensional analysis is a technique that was developed initially to make sure that one is comparing apples with apples (Bar-Meir 2021). That is a realization that the two sides of a physical equation have to equate the same physical quantities e.g. force must be equal to force and not pressure. Later the technique turned out to use more sophisticated and included the raise of dimensionless parameters. Basically dimensionless parameters/numbers are ratios of combination of physical quantities. For instance the matching a pin and hole, is determined by the ratio of the pin and the hole diameters. Simplistically stating, if the ratio is one, there is a match if the ratio is larger or smaller than one the set does not match.

While this idea seems trivial and insignificant, it turned out that this idea solve or help solve many problems in physics, engineering, chemistry and biology. For example, in biology, recently fish locomotion is determined a dimensional number

(Bar-Meir 2022). In fact, this idea recently was used to calculate spread Corona Virus. Over 67,000 papers and books were written using this technique for corona virus spread example of such paper (Rushdi and Rushdi 2020). Later, (even earlier) the dimensional analysis include the usage of these dimensionless parameters to differentiate between different zones. As all science disciplines, the Dimensional Analysis plagues with controversies such Buckingham Pi Theorem as oppose to Nusselt/Schmidt approach. In the great picture, the technique is a powerful tool to investigate and to be used by people from various area like medicine, biology, engineering, physics, mathematics etc.

This ability of the dimensional analysis to distinguish can be used to build free will zones map. The word map refers to ranges where the zones of deterministic actions reside and where the free will roams. Like all things in real life there will be zones that no clear answer can be determined easily and a debate will range on these different points.

5 Dimensional Analysis Usage for Free Will

The Dimensional Analysis can determine when randomness occurs when it does not. Suppose the stimuli appear on the background of prevailing “average situations” then the free will action does exist. For instance, when one is offered a glass of water when one is thirsty. The chances are that one will drink the water. On the other hand, when one is offered water the prevailing background is such none favorite conditions exist, the chances are that one will refuse the water. The meaning none favorite conditions it be something like suspect of poison in the water. The instinct is to drink the water, while the decision to override the instinct is the free will (perhaps). The idea of water is basically fundamentals for survival and it depends on the prevailing conditions. It is like a deer in a lake full with crocodiles, the deer face with the assessment of risks. This is a true for free will situations when the action can be in all kind of directions depending on the initial conditions (for those who do not like this term it means earlier conditions) which more likely to be random. Thus, the core of free will is the situation were “random velocity” determines the action, hence people have “free will” at that conditions.

Pavlov’s dog experiment in which the bell ringing creates a hunger reaction in dog is opposite of a free will. That is, the “computer” is (or can be) programmed to be deterministic. This well known phenomenon that the “computer” can be programmed in situations like cults. It is possible to (de)reprogram a person. Numerous examples can be provided for forcing deterministic behavior from people and other animals and later moving them to be with a free will. The change in from deterministic to free will perhaps can be measured in the wave length such as done by Libet (1999). Libet found that decision is done in the range of 100 mSec to 600 mSec in the time there is a possibility for veto control (ultimate free will). Libet measured the time of veto control takes effect to be about 0.5[sec]. Are “programmed”

people have a different (shorter) reaction time? It postulated here that the answer is yes. This time is not essential in the suggestion in this topic.

The time for decision according Libet is important in estimating whether the existence of free will occur. Thus, this time issue gives raise to the question which parts of the brain are fast and which parts can be overridden. To illustrate this point, many of the human actions controlled by primitive brain (Cerebellum). Are actions taken by this part are faster and almost impossible to override or the veto action requires additional “planing” time? These are the questions on further research can be carried out.

6 What are Pure Free Will Situations?

To provide a breakthrough in some areas, one has to look at the area from different angle. Reviewing the papers and books on the topic of “free will” is missing the definition of what constitute a free will. The lack of the definition or understanding what constitute free will is fundamental to meaningful understanding what is discussed.

So far the discussion dealt with temporary deterministic behavior, gray areas, the veto, butterfly effect. Now the focus has to turn on what is a pure free will situation. To intelligently discuss free will, one first must present what true free will situation is. The deterministic situation seems self explanatory. For example, a thirsty person is looking for something to the drink and one faces with several options. On the one hand, when there are several options for the liquid, then the person (might) has “free will” situation. On the other hand, if the person has only one possibility there is really no free will situation. The Dimensional Analysis suggests that under certain conditions there is a clear and pure “free will” situation. All the other situations fail somewhere in between “free will” and deterministic behavior. These situations are referred as situations without complete determination. That is, there is a tendency but not complete determination. In fact, this category is the very common. Even with randomness of the system there is a tendency for particular direction like water molecules in a pressure gradient field (sorry using engineering example, it basically flow under pressure has the tendency move to lower pressure).

When a group of individuals is given prescribe options, some individuals will choose option A while other will choose option B or C. It is said that if most individuals will choose one of the options then there is no pure “free will” situation. On the other hand, when there is distribution (e.g. option A, B, etc) it can be said there is a stronger “free will” situation (in dimensional analysis, it will said large option number). Then situation of election with only one candidate and one must vote is equivalent deterministic while the other extreme is many candidates. Note, when there are too many options, it changes the dynamic and it can be viewed as a limited options or no option at all.

The mechanics of how to apply the dimensional analysis

is more complicate topic and requires considerable investigation. In this paper the focus is on the introduction of several concepts to which look align to many in philosophy circles. It has to be mentioned that topics like macro and micro good will are part of this conversation and should be included in the dimensional analysis. However, this inclusion will complicate the arguments that presentation here and hence were avoided.

7 The Benefits of Measuring Free Will

The question is the foregoing has any effect on the life or it is just an academic discussion. It is hope if the ideas of measuring one free will could have impact on judicial system. There will be always judges and prosecutors who just want to promote their agenda for them self to get their benefits or they just being plain idiots. However, instituting study of this measuring tool for free will might be useful to make the judicial System more reasonable.

The free will understanding can have effects on the medical, education and training. This statement is self explanatory, the magnitude is not. For instance, one of the problem of education is the motivation. The education system is build around the free will doctrine while it is some kind of gray. This idea can effect how to increase the motivation. It seems as a logical step to used the technique as a foundation on how increase the motivation. While it is unknown if indeed that it is the case, yet, the possibilities warrant exploration. There several topics that remain unresolved and one should not expect all to be addressed in a single paper.

In the free will there is no another approach beside well established two camps. This exotic idea appeared as from the thin ether. This idea has not surfaced any book or article that is controlled by the establishment. In fact the advocating the scientific approach rather the philosophical approach is not expected to happen, if it was depend on the establishment. Yet, it is suggested these science developments should utilized with questions from the philosophical roam to the physical reality. This action is actually work of free will. The question is there any clear equation that govern by complex set processes in the brain (or the bodies). The characteristic of such equations are should study to exam whether the solution is unique and stable (that is a single solution and stable means no free will). Clearly answer to this question does not requires actual solution of the equation(s) or even writing them. Sometime knowing certain parameters might provide the hint if something is deterministic.

8 Summary

The paper is unique and presents topic of free will in a different light than all millions of papers and books written on the topic. First, the possibility gray zone is discussed. The issue that constitute a pure free will action scenario is presented. The idea of

using dimensional analysis is described, and what is the free will and what is the deterministic area. Clearly antagonistic reactions are expected and time will tell if any of the ideas presented in this paper will take a root.

Conflict of Interest

The authors Dr. Eliezer Bar–Meir and Genick Bar–Meir certify that they have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent–licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

Eliezer Bar–Meir **ORCID:** 0000-0001-9200-4196

Genick Bar–Meir **ORCID:** 0000-0003-3285-7837

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